

Deconstructing the Discourses on Manipuri Women

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Manipuri women are much adulated and glorified by various sections of society. The media also report their active participation in economic, civil and political life. This however represents only a slice of their lives. The larger picture that is woven around their private lives, which play out in a multitude of ways to define their place in society is invariably lost in this glorification. This paper traces the emergence of women, their participation in public life, and their glorification, to the epoch-making NupiLaan movement that took place in 1939. This event is observed to have sanctified women rising to the forefront in a variety of public concerns up to the present day. My paper intends to deconstruct this sanctified position accorded to Manipuri women. It analyses whether such public activism serves to unshackle them from the mundane but complex social challenges of being a woman. It examines their aspirations and the capacities they have to nurture their individual dreams independently. It argues that social realities confound them and they are not in tandem with their aspirations. The role of religion is also analyzed here. This paper thus tries to unearth their aspirations and the kind of realities they have to grapple with. Unique Individual achievements and excellence in any chosen field and the realities or challenges related thereto are not within the scope of this discussion. Rather it underlines how the paradox of public adulation tinged with private agonies complicate the understanding of the status of the Manipuri women.

Innate Consciousness or Other Forces?

Before getting into the nuances of the paper, I wish to clarify that Meiteis, Meitei Tribes and Meitei Pangals (Muslims) are together referred to as Manipuris as an ethnic group in common nomenclature. But the ethnonym Manipuri refers to the closer group of 'Meiteis'. Thus Manipuris can be understood as an exonym to encompass a wider group, whereas it is an endonym or autonym for the Meiteis. The endonym perspective is adopted in this paper and hence Meiteis and Manipuris have been used alternately. Manipuri women are sporadically and constantly lauded by the media as brave and courageous; especially for the active

roles they play in contemporary times. Noteworthy instances are that of IromSharmila fasting since the year 2000 for the cause of withdrawal of the Armed Forces Special Powers Act, 1958; hordes of women joining the men in the spate of the protests against the extension of the Government of India's call for extension of the ceasefire to Manipur in 2001; women taking the lead in seeking action against the guilty, when a little girl called Luiningla Elizabeth was kidnapped and found murdered in 2003; and that of the group of twelve elderly women who bared themselves in 2004 in front of the gate of the Kangla Fort in Imphal, which was then the headquarters of the Assam Rifles as a retaliation to the rape of ThangjamManoramaby the Armed

forces. These are but a few striking instances of women coming to the forefront in contemporary times, besides the innumerable rendezvous of women engaged in bandhs, strikes, dharnas etc. for issues affecting the civil and political fabric of Manipuri Society. However, it remains to be tested and proven whether such kind of an active participation in these spheres by the Manipuri women is an innate act of individual as well as collective boldness and consciousness; or is it history, society and culture making them to put their act together. It is essential to understand this because my aim is to explore if these acts of boldness, whether individual or collective, is unfurled within the domestic confines too, related to other mundane affairs, barring civil and political life. I then go on to explore how it has affected their aspirations, and what are the realities they have to encounter.

Manipuri Women in the Political Economy of Manipur: A Historical Context

History matters. It matters because mostly all societies tend to stand up in tacit solidarity of the forces that have played memorable roles in making their society the way it is, as they know it today. It can also be vice versa in that because society commemorates and glorifies that event, it assumes even more significance. Thus the nature of the event, and more so, the context of the event shapes peoples' perceptions and hence people tend to view it as significant or insignificant. This is how discourses shape perceptions, identities, opinions and activities in the social realm. A close examination of the role played by Manipuri women in historical

times, famously termed as the "Nupi (women) Laan (war)", proves to be a fine example of how intricately economy, polity and civil life are interrelated.

The active participation of Manipuri women in civil and political life can be traced back to the times of yore. In the ancient times, during the king's rule, much before menfolk started taking up arms as we know it today, Manipuri women led non-violent and peaceful movements against any injustice. They would also report any such acts of injustice, whether committed by the King himself or by his officials, to the King and thus seek justice. It is said that during Maharaj Chandrakirti's reign in Manipur, his wild game hunt for elephants (Shamutanba) was postponed upto the end of the harvest upon the representation of the women. However, there were two key incidents that marked the rise of the women's movement in Manipur. Popularly known as NupiLaan in Manipur's economic and political history, these two incidents happened during the time of British Superintendency; the first in 1904 and the second in 1939.

The chronicles of Manipur record that in 1904, the Assistant Superintendent's house was burnt and the people of Imphal were ordered to bring teak wood from Kabow (now in Myanmar) and to rebuild his house. The people protested against it, against which the Government ordered curfews. Despite this, women disobeyed the orders and entered the residence of the Political Agent and the Superintendent. The impact was so great that the Manipur Government required outside help to control the situation. Moreover, ultimately the British had to

build the houses at their own expense. This was a landmark event in the political history of Manipur, which is also perceived today as an overwhelming moment in the history not only of Manipuri women, but of Manipur itself. Another event though less noted in history was when, in 1925, the state authorities increased the water tax and there were widespread demonstrations against this measure. The main participants in this agitation were again women. Yambem (1976) asserts that we must note that these agitations were all led by the tradeswomen, as was the case during the women's agitation of 1939. It is thus pertinent to note how the marketplace occupied primarily by women even till today, has been the cradle of planned agitation by Manipuri women.

This particular event of 1939 was an epoch-making incident that marked the prominent rise and participation of Manipuri women in the state's political economy. It took place in December-January, 1938-39, when the harvest of Manipur was not satisfactory. The area under rice cultivation in Manipur between 1921 and 1939 increased by merely 18,838 acres, while the volume of rice exported increased by 2,92,174 maunds (One maund is equal to 37.3242 Kilograms in India). Thus domestic requirements were threatened. Rice export from Manipur reached an all-time record of 3,72,174 maunds in 1938, the year before the outbreak of the NupiLaan. Bad weather and increased exports resulted in severe shortage of rice. Women then filed a petition to the Darbar, (the highest original and appellate court, both in civil and criminal matters) to stop the rice export.

Thousands of women demonstrated before the Darbar Hall where their petition was being discussed. They insisted that the order to stop the rice export should be announced immediately. The Darbar announced the ban on exports but however agreed to the request of the Political Agent for the export of rice to the Kohima Civil Station. The Darbar not only reserved the right to stop this export anytime; it also expressed apprehensions about famine in Manipur. However, under another resolution passed on the same day, the Darbar approved a scheme whereby no rice could be exported from Manipur without the permission of the Political Agent. This was perceived as dubious and deceitful. Moreover, barring a few conditions of restraint, the actual ban lasted for only forty days from September 14 to November 21, 1939. It would perhaps not be wrong, therefore, to assume that the decision to re-open rice export trade by the Darbar on November 21, 1939, was taken under heavy pressure from the Maharaja, who in turn was pressurised by the Cart Tax monopolists and other merchants. This reopening of the rice export was directly responsible for the outbreak of NupiLaan on December 13, 1939 (Yambem, 1976).

It is important to note that Manipur is an agricultural economy, and even today, rice plays a crucial role in Manipuri society. Women are actively involved in the entire supply chain starting with sowing up to selling of the final produce in the market. Thus the significance and role of women in the economy of the state is indeed decisive, and a boycott of the market by them would mean a virtual hartal of the whole bazar, severely

affecting the economy (Yambem, 2011). However, since the objective of my paper is not to describe in detail about these historic events, but rather to establish context as to how these events marked the rise of Manipuri women as active participants in the political economy of Manipur, I end my narrative about these events here. Nevertheless, one must deeply appreciate the determination and collective participation amongst the women who agitated on that historic day, especially since the incident did not occur at the behest of any male leader; nor with their support and participation. Such boldness definitely is admirable and thus this event is sacrosanct in the annals of Manipuri history. The courage and strength of the Manipuri women of today springs forth from such a sanctified pedestal; and thus inherently acquires the aura of historical, cultural and societal sanction.

The Social Web of History, Economy and Polity

It is popular knowledge today among social scientists, especially in India, that trading and vending of items ranging from items of daily consumption such as vegetables, indigenous fruits, fish (which forms a key component of Manipuri diet) etc. to goods such as the *Phanek* (the local sarong), *Innaphee* (traditional shawls worn by women along with the *Phanek*), and other handloom products are the domain of women in the marketplace. Dubbed as the "Ima (meaning mother) Market", where married women of all age groups (with a majority of them being above their forties) converge for trading and vending purposes, the famous

Khwairamband Bazaar in Imphal is a place pulsating with life and vigour. It is believed to have been founded by King Khagemba around the year 1580. Over two thousand women occupy regular stalls while an even larger number are seated outside, sometimes left at the mercy of the state administration for unlicensed hawking and vending. The whole market has always been managed by the women and persists till today. Apart from the economic activities, the market also plays the role of an important hub for social and political interaction. It was this aspect of the Khwairamband Bazaar that played a crucial role in the outbreak of the NupiLaan in 1939, which marked the strong rise of political consciousness among the people of Manipur (Yambem, 2011). Moreover, commonality of needs and aspirations also added flavour to the movement.

It is therefore pertinent for us to understand how and why women traders and vendors of Manipur emerged, assumed, and continue to remain significant economic actors. This can once again be traced back to history. Every able-bodied man had to render enormous feudal services during both war and peacetime at the time of the Kings' reign. This was known as "lallupkaba". Historical testimonies and the assertion of several scholars point out that the existence of this institution or system was responsible in pushing the women to take an active part in the family economy. Barua and Devi (2004) quote Brown (1879) and state, "This is some kind of forced labour prevalent in Manipur. This institution has very ancient origin in Manipur". They also describe how lallup was based on the

assumption that every male between the ages of 17 and 60 were required to render their services for the state, without remuneration for a certain number of days (There was no rigidly fixed number of days and varied as per the King's instructions.). This system was abolished in 1892. The noblemen of the society were however exempted from it, while the majority of the population had to undergo this process. Thus the system directly or indirectly compelled the women to take up an active role in economic activities. This consequently paved the way for a large section of women being engaged in trading and vending. Singh (1975) asserts that recruiting men thus appeared to be a system the King had adopted, in order to strengthen their forces against the continued hostility with the Burmese. Such a practice necessitated that the men would therefore frequently stay away from their homes, which further increased the responsibility of the Meitei women. They accordingly began to take up petty trade and also sought to acquire such skills and techniques as would help them attain self-reliance. As time passed, such petty trade and marketing became the monopoly of the women. Males were discouraged from encroaching upon this ascribed female domain of the economy to the extent that the kings punished those male members who tried to stay among the women traders. Collective resistance of women traders from encroachment upon their sphere of activities and the royal patronage that they received, further strengthened the position of women in trade and marketing. The significance of the women's market was thus reinforced by the fact that

proclamation of royal decrees, announcement of vital information, collection of taxes etc. all took place here. The fact that it is located in the heart of the capital and very close to the King's Palace helped. The women traders and vendors thus served as a vital channel of communication flow from the centre to the periphery. They brought news about events in various parts of the State when they came to the market and took back home whatever information they gathered while at work. Thus they participated in more than just a passive manner in the political economy of the State. Their profession made them interact not only among themselves but also with customers from all walks of life. They consequently acquired a strong sense of cohesiveness, solidarity, fearlessness, mutual dependency and co-operation through their professional engagements (Sanatomba, 2003).

Thus the role of women in Manipuri society was quite prominent from a very early stage. In 1886, Dun stated about the type of freedom enjoyed by the women of Manipur. He (1886) observed, "all the marketing is done by the women, all the works of buying and selling in public, carrying to and fro of articles to be sold, and whilst at home, they are busy employed in weaving and spinning". The Gazetteer of Manipur 1786 records that all the transactions of the kingdom were conducted by women in the open space and such activities took place in the mornings. These definitely have transformed now with both men and women being engaged in various acts of trading and vending. The exception is only of the Khwairamband market area, which is still dominated by

women, except for a few odd peddling and hawking by men. The marketplace is also abuzz with brisk activities from early morning till evening. New sheds and structures constructed by the government have replaced open spaces mostly; where the shopkeeper/ license holder has to pay tax for it. Women from all across Manipur come to this market to sell their wares as stated earlier. This is a glaring example of how these women are struggling for their existence. They are 'struggling' because studies suggest that it is not purely by sheer choice that a majority of them are engaged in these activities. It is often because that's the only choice they can make and have access to. This argument is substantiated in the later parts of the paper.

Role of Manipuri Men in the NupiLaan Movement

It is essential to understand whether the men played any role in this particular movement because the coexistence of men and women in any society is natural. It is only the relations between them that differ, and the roles they play, which then go on to determine the type of society. Therefore, for a better analysis, I intend to explore and understand whether the Manipuri men played any kind of role; whether implicit or explicit during the NupiLaan movement. Yambem (1976) records that on December 12, 1939, the Branch Secretary of the Nikhil Manipuri Mahasabha (NMM) along with others requested the elders of the Mahasabha to discuss the agitation of the women. The Mahasabha, however, declined to do so. It instead suggested that an appeal should be made to the Judicial Members of the Darbar. Unable to decide, these

members of the Mahasabha had no alternative but to wait for the arrival of the President of the Mahasabha, Hjam Irabot Singh, who was then away at Cachar. It is significant to note that the NMM was originally known as the Nikhil Manipuri Hindu Mahasabha and was founded in Manipur in 1934 under the patronage of Maharaja Churachand Singh who was the president of the organization. All tasks were carried out by Hjam Irabot who was the vice-president. Irabot changed the name of the Sabha by dropping the Hindu off the original name and also changed it into a political party.

On December 13, a meeting called by the dissenting members of the Mahasabha was held at the Police Bazar, as the Khwairamband Bazar market was under a hartal. This was a small gathering which passed off peacefully. The President arrived in Imphal on December 16, and with this, the NupiLaan entered a new phase. The upsurge which so far had been led solely by the women, now received male support. The next day, the President called a meeting of the working committee of the Nikhil Manipuri Mahasabha to discuss the NupiLaan. It was in this meeting that conflict between Irabot and other members were revealed. The other members of the Mahasabha were against the movement, and Irabot thus opted out of the Mahasabha. On December 24, 1939, he formed a new political organisation called Manipur PrajaSamelini at a meeting held at the Police Grounds (Yambem, 1976).

Thus abetted with renewed vigour through support from the men, the revolting women spoke up against the weakness of the Darbar members as well

as the unacceptable physical assault on the women with guns and bayonets by the state's functionaries. Unfortunately, this tumultuous uprising spearheaded by women and comprising only of women, came to an end, as a majority of the people began fleeing from Imphal for safety as the Second World War approached Manipur.

Regarding male participation, it may hence be hypothesized that if Irabot had not lent his support, the uprising may not have acquired the political tone that it eventually did, and may have remained purely a women's agitation. Adequate information is unavailable from known literature to prove or disprove this. However, it must be emphasized that despite the role of Irabot and the participation of men, it was and remains essentially a women's movement. The boycott of the market for more than one and a half years certainly convinced the state authorities that the women of Manipur could take up any form of agitation once they were convinced of their purpose. It would perhaps not be very far from the truth to conclude that the NupiLaan, which started as a rice export control agitation directed against the economic policies of the Maharaja and the Marwari monopolists, later on changed its character to become a movement for constitutional and administrative reforms in Manipur. The uniqueness of the movement, however, lies in the fact that after the end of the Second World War, which also broke out at that time, it was the women of Manipur who were at the forefront of change.

Women's Economic Contribution

In the light of discussions about women

playing an active role in the civil and political life, which was manifested through the NupiLaan agitation. I once again reiterate that this agitation sprung from the fact that their economic avenues were being threatened by the uncontrolled export of rice from Manipur. I further assert that the economic contribution of Manipuri women especially in the family economy is profound. In the rural areas, it is a common sight to see women working in the paddy fields early in the morning. They also work as hired labour in others' paddy fields. Apart from this, every family in the rural areas of Manipur have a kitchen garden in the surrounding campus. The older women generally go to the market to sell their products. Very young and especially unmarried women do not engage in these activities. Walking two to three miles with basket loads of vegetables on their heads is quite a common sight. They thus help supplement the family's income. Both men and women alike engage in fishing too, as fish forms a significant part of the Manipuri diet.

Weaving is another very important source of income for women both in rural and urban areas. In the past, almost every married woman would receive a loom as a part of her marriage gifts from her parents. Manipuri women are extremely skilled in weaving and the handloom fabric of Manipur has always been an important commodity for export both in the Indian and international markets. The market-scene especially for such goods in Manipur is thus dominated by women. Embroidery is also an important source of income generation. Thus, women from earlier times itself have been very active in

small-scale internal trade and commerce. The hub of all commercial activities dealing with daily items are centered on women. It may consequently be inferred that active participation in the economic affairs of the household and in the unorganized sector ascribed an implicit position as well as necessity to the Manipuri women to participate in an equally active manner in civil and political life. Besides this, the self-consciousness to participate in such decision making that will affect their livelihood is another aspect.

Hinduisation and its Impact on Manipuri Society and Manipuri Women

Although strands of Hinduism were reportedly penetrating into the Kingdom of Manipur as early as the fifteenth century (Sircar, 1984), it was in the early eighteenth century during the reign of Maharaja Garib Niwaz (1709-1748) that Vaishnavism spread in Manipur, particularly in the valley. It was then patronised as the royal religion and was further reinforced with the influx of Brahmins from North India, who gradually married the Manipuri women and settled down. The Meiteis, having embraced Hinduism, thereby, began to practice social stratification under the Hindu caste system. This had the effect of restricting the social relations between the 'sanskritised' Meiteis and the hill-tribes.

S. Bandopadhyay (2009) says:

Hinduism is a religion which has the innate capacity of assimilating easily other streams of ideas within itself in an absolute oneness. The main philosophy of the Vedic Hindu religion was that there was one god who was omnipresent

in all ages and places. He was worshipped in various ways and various forms but he remained the one and indivisible. All deities were but different forms and names of the same supreme god. The task of accepting the deities worshipped by the tribes, as a result of the Sanskritisation process would therefore gradually be assimilated into the fold of mainstream Hinduism.

Sircar (1984: 105) notes that the royal temple of Govindaji thus became the epicentre of a new elite culture under royal patronage. However, the Meitei traditional culture which had a strong base amongst the peasantry, could not be totally replaced by the new religion, which was perceived as an imposition by them. Traditional Lai (God) worship persisted as a part of Meitei family worship and Hinduism and the royal temple was accepted more as an institution created by the king than as a religion of the people. The Lai Haraoba (Merrymaking of the Gods) ceremony, an ancient Meitei ritual, thus continued to remain an important religious ritual of the people even during the height of the Vaishnava influence. It continues to remain so till today. Sircar also points out that in Meitei society, despite the patriarchal social structure, there is mutual partnership and respect between the sexes and women's power is not assertive at the cost of the prevailing 'harmony' in the man-woman relationship. She additionally talks about the recent renaissance of Meitei religious and cultural practices and the probabilities of de-Sanskritisation of Manipuri society. However, it is my observation that the lofty Hindu ideals of womanhood has been so entrenched in the Meitei society that it appears

unlikely for times to come that 'Meiteisation' and any such de-Sanskritisation would eventually lead to the reassertion of the social freedom of women. If any kind of assertion for women's place in society does occur, it will be attributed to other factors of the modern world and less due to de-sanskritisation.

It is nonetheless interesting to note that Meitei women are carving out for themselves a more prominent position in the Vaishnava religious system which had earlier relegated women to an inferior position in the religious structure (Sircar 1984: 108-111). One instance of such a niche in Vaishnavism is the Nupipala (Bandopadhyay, 2009). Vaishnavism is thus being sought to be moulded within and around Meitei religious practices thus making the process of assimilation unique where ethnic practices continue to abound. Dance and drama had been a significant part of Manipuri culture. Vaishnavism had thus adopted dance as an important tool in the process of sanskritisation of the Manipuris (Shakespeare, 1913).

Hinduism practices and propagates the concept of pollution and purity. If and when a Brahmin man marries a woman of a lower caste, their children are still Brahmin but the woman is not considered one amongst the Brahmins (Allen: 62). Moreover, non-Brahmin women are not permitted to cook for Brahmins (especially elders). In all totality, strict observance of caste rules were not prevalent in the public arena and this helped in greater participation of women in public life. They thus continued to engage freely in their activities of weaving, selling their wares, and engaging in various other ways of

economic sustenance. Women thus continued to play important roles in the economy and polity of the state. Dun (1975) also concurs that an important feature of the modern Manipuri society, which is quite unique for a Hindu society, is the prominent socio-economic role of the women. He further points out that despite their industriousness, women hold a very inferior position and are considered more as "goods and chattels" than as persons to be treated with honour and consideration (1975: 23). McCulloh (1980: 19) adds, "though useful and laborious (they) are but indifferently treated ... A man can put away his wife without any fault on her part, and if a person of influence, he may do so without it being noticed. Women are really the slave of her husband, they are sold in satisfaction of their debts". He argues that women thus become victims of polygamy and other forms of male oppression. All these discussions appear paradoxical because despite these Brahmannical practices related to purity, social evils like Sati and child marriage associated with Hinduism, did not rupture the Manipuri society (Shakespeare, 1913). Yet on the other hand, women's position as compared to men were always low.

In terms of pollution and purity, it is a common practice that no Hindu Vaishnavite woman is to enter the kitchen before taking a morning bath. Moreover, during her menstrual cycle, she is prohibited to enter the kitchen as well as come in physical contact with other male members of the household, especially elders. Thus we see that in the public arena, Hinduism did not pose much of a threat to the status of women. However, in the private domain, there

were staunch pollution and purity related practices, thus resulting in an inferior status particularly within the confines of families and households. These were thus instrumental in shaping societal opinion about women. Shakespear (1913: 417) also noted that regarding diet, Manipuris are very orthodox, and in many cases even more conventional than Hindus generally are today. He attributes these partly to the relative isolation of the Manipuris, and partly to their desire to distinguish themselves from the non-sanskritised Hill tribes, who have adopted Christianity instead around the later half of the nineteenth century.

Hinduism and Women's Position: A Paradox

Sircar (1984) reiterates that Brahmannical Hinduism, courtesy the royal patronage it had been receiving for the last four centuries, has not really worked its way to corrode the status of Manipuri women entirely. Despite being rooted in a more traditional and tribal-like social composition; women's economic independence, mutual support and solidarity continue to be the cornerstone around which Manipuri women realize their powers of being "Female" and of feminism. Continuing the argument about the paradoxical nature of women's status in Manipuri society, this proposition of Sircar is refutable on many accounts. Although historically Manipuri women came together towards striving for economic independence in the backdrop of necessity created by the absence of their men for prolonged periods (refer Lallup), the Meitei society is definitely not free from social exploitation of women

common in patriarchal set-ups. Sircar tries to maintain that there is 'acceptance' as well as 'defiance' of male superiority; but however cites more evidence of social injustice in the family structure and marriage customs of the Meitei. The Meitei woman is encouraged as well as expected to uphold the lofty ideals of patience and tolerance, as is the case with any other average Hindu woman, even in the course of a disturbed marriage. 'Male superiority' is emphasised in every sphere of Meitei family life, and the male child is accorded importance. It is my own observation that newly wedded couples are showered with good wishes from elders, relatives, friends, family members alike to be 'blessed' with a male child. Moreover, the Meitei society still practice polygamy especially in the rural hinterlands, on the pretext of bearing a male progeny. Historical records state that after the Manipuri-Burmese War of 1817, and the seven years of devastation of the Manipuri countryside that followed it, the male population of Manipur was greatly reduced. The Anglo-Manipuri War of 1891, further reduced the male population of Manipur resulting in the greater acceptance of the practice of polygamy, and increased dependence on women for the upkeep of the family. It is assumed that this was one of the factors that promoted the practice of polygamy. Sircar (1984:81) also noted that the practice of polygamy is so common even in the urban areas of Manipur in recent times. This is further confirmed by my own observations. She however does not specify the existence of any collective resistance against such a degrading practice. It is once again my observation

as also corroborated by Sircar (1984: 85) that the only form of protest seems to be that of a passive individual gloom. Such a kind of resistance has no bearing upon the malady, and women continue to suffer. Ancient war time sex ratios cannot and must not be allowed to persist as any semblance of a justification for such a degrading practice.

Besides this anomaly of polygamy, another feature commonly seen in Meitei society is that of forceful abduction (Phaaba). A man may forcefully abduct a girl of his choice but it would be later interpreted as an elopement (Chenba). The latter is different because here it assumes that the girl went of her own free will and inducement of fear or force was not involved. Though a girl has the right to refuse marriage to her abductor, parents, friends and relatives generally convince her to do so as after such an abduction or elopement, her chances of marriage to another man especially as a first wife are highly grim. In the olden days, the fear of being kidnapped would constantly haunt an unmarried Meitei girl and restrict her movements. This also induced another dimension to the problem faced by the Manipuri women. It hampered her self-development especially in terms of attainment of education. However, with the advent of modernity and its resultant changes, the problem has taken a different dimension. Now, women in Manipur no longer prefer to confine themselves to the home and hearth. Whether such a factor has a direct bearing on violence against women in Manipur is yet to be tested. But crimes like rape that was unheard of in Manipuri society is acquiring a place of very significant concern today

as per news reports. This leaves the Manipuri women's position basically similar to that of women in any other part of India, despite her glorified economic independence, status, and self-expression. Sircar (1984:57) quotes a Meitei professor in this regard who said, "Do not feel deceived by the economic role of the Meitei women. In reality they have a much inferior status than men". Social norms impose an unseen expectation upon the Manipuri women to marry in order to gain social security. Social status is accorded to the woman who bears a male progeny. For instance, a woman who has a male child is selected to take the initiative while going with marriage proposals on behalf of friends and relatives. Such a woman is also given a pride of place in various rites and rituals related to the Meitei marriage, thus treating her presence as "auspicious". Besides this, the married woman is also expected to uphold all the qualities of a "good Hindu" woman. Reality is thus a far cry from the refrain adopted by scholars of the high social status of the 'independent' Manipuri woman. The picture portrayed and understood by various scholars that glorifies the Manipuri woman's independence, taking cues only from the eminence of the Khwairamband market and the role played by women in terms of public demonstrations related to civil and political issues is only one-sided. I will present in the later paragraphs some data related to why such glorification in the face of private agony induced by evils such as polygamy, taboos against women who have not borne male children, or inequalities even in day-to-day decision making, does not serve to undo their inferior status. Rather it

promotes a false myth of their independence and prowess. Hence, we can emphasise here that participation in economic as well as civil and political life did not really influence the social life and status of the Manipuri woman as her private domain remains fettered, which in turn have various implications in public life.

Slicing the Discourses that Stereotype Manipuri Women

Feminist studies have been mirroring each other's arguments in several cases, where they attribute the low status of women to patriarchal practices in society. It is uncertain and can only be surmised whether ancient Manipuri society (Bimola, 1988) was matriarchal, like any other ancient society in the past. Scholars like John F McLennan (1865), Lewis Henry Morgan (1877), and Edward Burnett Tylor (1899) have strongly advocated the matriarchy theory. Other scholars like Riane Eisler have promoted matriarchal societies that worshipped an ancient great goddess. The depiction of the female as an ancient goddess in the form of Panthoibi, serves as evidence of the existence of a female goddess in Meitei religious practices. Mythologies of matriarchy also abound in various ancient societies. However, dated history records Manipur being ruled by a King and not by a Queen. Therefore, adopting Vaishnavism under the patronage of the then King of Manipur, wherein Hinduism was made the official religion of Manipur in 1717 A.D., cannot be cited as a cause of transformation from matriarchy to patriarchy. Nonetheless, the fact that with the advent of Hinduism in the early eighteenth century, things began to

change, especially for women has to be recognised.

Needless to reiterate though, the NupiLaan movement sprung forth amongst the section of population engaged widely in the Khwairamband market. However, the truth is that this glorified section of women actually long for change in their personal lives. Manipur is fairly lagging behind in terms of development in the all India scenario. For instance, the Planning Commission reports that the per capita income in Manipur is Rupees 27,332 as compared to Rupees 63,547 in Tamil Nadu and Rupees 63,549 in Gujarat, at current prices in 2009-10. Huirem (2008, unpublished thesis), analysed the aspirations of a section of the population in Khwairamband market with a view to understand their perspectives towards "the right to development". The findings are presented in the following paragraphs.

Only a small section of the women traders and vendors feel that their work is just enough to satisfy their basic needs, which could be attributed to the fact that several of them consider selling their wares as a way of keeping the tradition of weaving alive. It has already been mentioned earlier that weaving was practiced in all Meitei households and a young bride would compulsorily get a loom from her parents at the time of leaving her natal home on account of marriage. Besides this, it may be noted that since historical days, the women from the relatively better-off families would engage in production and sales of handloom products, as opposed to those engaged in trading and vending of vegetables and other items of daily consumption. Moreover, many elderly

women look forward to coming to the marketplace as a way of socialisation. What is noteworthy, however is that a larger majority underlined the lack of alternatives, the fatigue and drudgery involved, and their own compulsions for sustenance. These highlights the sense of helplessness and hopelessness amongst them. Family life and living standards too were unsatisfactory. The better educated and younger women are keen to have a regular salaried job. This once again underlines the sense of helplessness, lack of alternatives and the element of compulsion that is prevalent in their much glorified economic independence.

Age brings about a certain edge in terms of personal liberties. In certain households, family members were against their selling of wares in the market as their economic conditions had improved over time; with younger educated members earning better incomes. However, the women, especially the elderly, preferred carrying on with their routine work as it gave them a higher sense of self-worth owing to economic independence. Moreover, they also like it as they get to mingle with their peer-group and thus serves as a socialisation for them. In many cases, it had become an essential feature of their daily existence. Majority of them are purely on a daily wage existence, where the importance of education is yet to be appreciated. Thus low levels of education persist owing to affordability as well as lack of awareness of its significance. The common opinions were that girls were not sent to school in those days. They also questioned how a girl will benefit by going for higher studies. However, as is noted in all underpri-

vileged homes, majority of them felt that it is a girl's duty to help at home and also considering the economic constraints, it was better to educate the son who is a pillar of strength for their future. Moreover, besides the lack of awareness of the benefits of education, early marriage and distance of schools as well as the lack of access to girls' schools were also prominently cited. Data thus corroborates findings of several earlier studies on women that her plight is considerably lower than her male counterpart. She is always a victim of her family and society in terms of neglect and secondary treatment.

They feel disadvantaged owing to their economic condition and social status, as well as their gender. It is significant to note that despite their own low education background, they aspire for quality education for their children in the hope of a better life. They expressed that education will help secure employment as well as self-reliance. Such expressions by them underscore the fact that compulsions for sustenance keep them in their occupation of trading and vending. These are the harsh realities they have to live with. However, aspirations differ. So glorification of these women in terms of their economic independence serves only a myopic outlook.

Recontextualising the NupiLaan Movement and Status of Manipuri Women

Social roles and tasks tend to get stereotyped on the basis of gender, propelled by intra-society as well as inter-society norms. Sobel (1993) firmly believes that occupational involvement generates strong political participation,

particularly, across homogeneous groups, and more so if the problem is also commonly felt. He hypothesizes that occupational involvement, other factors being constant, generates political participation, and that the influence from work to politics occurs across similar levels of formality. This was evident in the outbreak of the NupiLaan movement, where they had all the commonalities of work place, namely, khwairambandmarket; and the problem of unceasing rice export in a time of increasing scarcity, which was a problem of huge social and political magnitude that would affect all the families in Manipur.

According to Milbrath and Goel (1977: 53), "Political participation is a learned social role". Pateman (1970:42-43) further agrees that as participation increases, their own individual ability to participate also, the better able they become to do so. Mason (1982:60) has summed up very aptly by concluding that participation "breeds participation". Sobel (1993: 341) seals these arguments by stating that "regular repetition of similar activities including decision making develops as an orientation to action or inaction, the flow of influence runs generally from work to politics." He also makes a very interesting point here. He states:

Because influence transfers most directly across congruent levels of formality, formal occupational involvement, such as having enough authority to direct others, should generate more formal political involvement, such as electoral activity. In essence, the relationship occurs because exercising authority is formal and typically rule-oriented like voting.

Less formally structured occupational involvement such as participation in workplace decisions (work participation) should generate involvement in community activity that is similarly less formally structured.

The women primarily being studied are those who are coming for work at the Khwairambandmarket, which is an unorganised sector of the economy. It is naturally less formally structured. They are thus able to generate those kind of community activities that are less formally structured which are seen in contemporary Manipur such as protests, gheraoetc. To cooperate and coordinate for such momentary uprisings on various issues, which may or may not be long lived enough to become a movement, unlike the epoch-making NupiLaan movement requires relatively less formal structuring. However, to unshackle the woman from the chains of subordination requires a more formally structured involvement. Moreover, such public rallies and protests such as justice for those arrested without warrant, or encounter deaths, or abuse and violence against women during counter-insurgency operations, have a massive public sympathy wave. In the context of Manipur, there is no 'other' in these kinds of protests as it is in the larger public interest; and most importantly it involves both men and women alike. These take place in the public domain. However, what a woman is experiencing within her family is only best known to her; best disclosed by her; as well as best protected by her. Yet, whether it is domestic violence which no doubt occurs in their own private worlds; or the inferior status accorded to women; or the expectations that come

by virtue of being a Hindu; generating community involvement and participation to overcome them requires a far greater and stronger formal structure of participation and long lasting organised involvement. No doubt the collectivity of incidences that bundle up as a common issue that trouble public life for the Manipuris, namely, unfair treatment by armed personnel to men and women alike can be looked at from the lens of a social movement. Conversely, advocating the cause of private agonies, which have a much larger and life-encompassing social implications, is a different challenge, especially when it gender relations come into play.

To understand social movements further, the broad definition of a social movement given by McCarthy and Zald (1973) is presented:

It includes all who in any form support the general ideas of the movement. Social movements contain social movement organisations, the carrier organisations that consciously attempt to coordinate and mobilize supporters. In the traditional view, social movements are dependent upon their participating members.

They further add:

Social movements range from those that are radical and all-embracing, aimed at totally changing the structure of society, to specifically focussed reform attempts. They encompass idea movements aimed at changing the world by changing individual thought and movements tied to specific ideologies and tactics. At the level of social movement organisations they include in some degree radical and clandestine terrorist groups, retreatist sects that revalue the world, reform

oriented political action groups, and interest groups aimed at changing a law or policy to benefit its members.

Taking a cue from the above, one can very well argue that to bring about change in the Manipuri woman's private world as well as her social standing, all the requirements namely support, belief in a common ideology, participating members, and organisations are lacking. To date there has been no protest or rallies that propagate women's rights per se. All major unrests such as the rally against Thangjam Manorama, even though it concerned a woman, have been against one commonly identified adversary, namely, the state in general, and the armed forces in particular. Advocating the general cause of women has so far not been the top agenda for protests even if the issue concerned women and the agitations were led and participated by women only. Thus the valour of the Manipuri woman has always been limited to her upfront role in civil protests regarding matters related to the state's governance, and in more recent times, with a sole focus on the army's misdoings.

To take the argument further, we can seek answers as to why there is an absence of organised women's resistance to the humiliating and degrading practices like polygamy. In today's free-thinking era, is it still justified to look at the widowed woman a symbol of misfortune? Why are the norms of pollution and purity so strictly drawn only for women? Perhaps the Manipuri woman would once again come to the forefront if the handloom industry for which Manipur is famous, is gradually monopolised by mainland business

houses. Weaving and handloom, as stated earlier, acquires symbolic significance in Manipuri history and culture; and merits due attention. On the other hand, issues that will undo the prevailing gender dynamics require an unshackling of the deeply entrenched ideas of male-female position in society. It appears that Manipur will take a long time to achieve a state of gender equilibrium. There are some positive indicators though. For example, the Manipur Census Report (2011) reports that the sex ratio in Manipur was 978:1000 in 2001. It has become more favourable in 2011 and is recorded at 992:1000. The same Report also states that out of an increase of 457647 literates during the decade 2001 -2011, rural areas accounted for 229282 and urban areas 228365. Yet another important data is that the gap in literacy rate among males and females has reduced from 19.8 in 2001 to 13.7 in 2011. It is hoped that increased education will definitely end practices like polygamy and wipe out such other taboos that pertain to women.

Besides these, there are other causes for alarm too in the evolving Manipuri society. 46 rape cases, 34 cases of assault with the intent to outrage the modesty of a woman, and 21 domestic abuse cases were recorded in 2012. Moreover, 101 cases of kidnapping were also recorded in the same year. Besides, kidnapping, which has a semblance of social sanction in the context of "Phaaba" (stated earlier while discussing about Hinduism), the other incidences have been relatively unknown to Manipuri society. Another cause for concern is the increasing numbers of divorces. According to the State Family

Court Report, there were 150 divorces in 2011. This is despite the exaltation of the feminine virtues of submission and tolerance.

Summing Up

We had noted in the earlier discussion related to the role of men in the success of the NupiLaan movement, albeit a late entry. Hence, it can be concluded that in the absence of equal if not strong participation by menfolk too, towards the emancipation of the status of Manipuri women, no movement can hold sway. The 'Meiteisation' and de-sanskritisation wave that is seen in contemporary Manipuri society and its impact on women is yet to be seen and tested. Except for a few odd instances of permitting and sanctifying female participation in rites and rituals that were earlier marked only for males, noteworthy instances of female deification is still rare to come by. In the discussion related to Hinduism, it had been highlighted how Sircar (1984) feels that women are not keen to assert themselves in ways where they feel that it will disturb the existing male-female harmony. Nonetheless, with the onset of modernity and its accompanying complexities, it is difficult to predict the trajectory. Moreover, increasing economic independence propelled by education in today's egalitarian oriented era will also serve as another force that will change Manipuri society and particularly the status of women.

Gee (2005) highlights that language is one of the key instruments in establishing the content of a discourse comprising of "social activities, identities and politics, far beyond 'giving and getting information'". Thus by

continually glorifying and filling the discourses on Manipuri women with such glories of public activism related to civil and political issues, the microcosm of their private lives as a "woman" in Manipuri society is lost in the macrocosm of the public acts of glory and heroism. Gee (2005:23) further argues thus:

We continually and actively build and rebuild our worlds not just through language but through language used in tandem with actions, interactions, non-linguistic symbol systems, objects, tools, technologies and distinctive ways of thinking, valuing, feeling, and believing. Sometimes what we build is quite similar to what we have built before; sometimes it is not. But language-in-action is always and everywhere an active building process.

It will be interesting to see if the same group of women in the Khwairamband market who had spearheaded the glorious NupiLaan movement for a better Manipur will once again rise to the occasion on account of promoting an egalitarian society from a gender perspective. Having acquired a place of sanctity, women's agitations in Manipur today range from a variety of concerns related to agitations against domestic violence and rape. However, as stated earlier, these are yet to acquire an organised and committed involvement that can take on the shape of something close to a woman's rights movement. Moreover, these issues have never been able to garner explicit support from the men. In so far as one major section of the society, namely, men remain out of the context of involvement, it will be a gargantuan task to achieve a gender-egalitarian society. Besides this, in a

modernising world, the measures that they adopt such as moral policing, an example being KainaKatpa (any woman assumed to be found having an unacceptable relationship with a man is forced to marry each other), are not friendly for social development.

Individual lives are shaped largely by the societies in which we live in; and societies in turn are shaped largely by our social histories. This is of course not to deny the reverse process at both levels. However, the very detailed discussion about the social history of Manipuri women in this paper is aimed at demystifying the notions that prevail about these women. It also highlights how being at the forefront for all things that pertain to Manipur does not necessarily endow them with the power to espouse their own rights from the gender lens. To conclude, I reiterate that social action on the lines of a NupiLaan movement which was instrumental in turning around the state during crises like a near famine situation in its history may perhaps be desirable in pushing forward women's rights in Manipur.

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